

SIGNAL ANALYSIS USING SIGNAL SPECTRUM AND FAST FOURIER TRANSFORM (FFT) TECHNIQUES

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Аннотация

Статья посвящена изучению теоретических основ, практических методов и технического аппарата спектрального анализа сигнала. В статье рассматривается важность спектрального анализа, его роль в анализе сигналов на основе их частотного состава и его роль в повышении эффективности систем передачи. Приведена информация о трех различных типах методов спектрального анализа – параллельных, последовательных и комбинированных методах анализа. Также поясняется важность анализа сигналов, определения их спектрального состава и оптимизации сигналов с использованием рядов Фурье и их комплексных и тригонометрических представлений, методов быстрого преобразования Фурье (БПФ). В статье также рассматриваются возможности анализа сигналов в реальном времени с использованием цифровых технологий и достижений микроэлектроники. Эти работы служат важным инструментом при анализе телекоммуникаций, информационных технологий и электронных систем.

Ключевые слова

Спектральный анализ, сигнал, частотный состав, ряд Фурье, быстрое преобразование Фурье, БПФ, методы анализа, параллельный анализ, последовательный анализ, комбинированный анализ, обработка сигналов, телекоммуникации, информационные технологии, микроэлектроника, цифровые технологии, оптимизация сигналов.

Annotation

This article is devoted to the study of the theoretical foundations, practical methods and technical equipment of spectral analysis of signals. The article presents the importance of spectral analysis, its role in analyzing signals according to their frequency composition and in increasing the efficiency of transmission systems. Information is provided about three types of spectral analysis methods - parallel, serial and combined analysis methods. It also explains the importance of

analyzing signals using the Fourier series and its complex and trigonometric forms, fast Fourier transform (FFT) methods, determining their spectral composition and optimizing the signal. The article also considers the possibilities of real-time analysis of signals using digital technologies and the development of microelectronics. These works serve as an important tool in the analysis of telecommunications, information technologies and electronic systems.

Keywords

Spectral analysis, signal, frequency composition, Fourier series, fast Fourier transform, FFT, analysis methods, parallel analysis, sequential analysis, combined analysis, signal processing, telecommunications, information technology, microelectronics, digital technologies, signal optimization.

The concept of spectral analysis is one of the main organizational parts of technical analysis and plays an important role in determining the characteristics of telecommunication signals. Spectral analysis is one of the signal processing methods that allows you to describe, explain and evaluate the frequency composition of the analyzed signal. The main task of spectral analysis is to determine the class of the analyzed signal and the characteristics of the transmission system by frequency characteristics.

Spectral analysis consists of the following operations:

determining the frequency values that make up the signal spectrum;

determining the frequency intervals between the spectrum components;

measuring the signal spectrum width;

determining the transmission (modulation) rate using the signal spectrum width;

determining the type of modulation (manipulation) and its parameters: modulation depth, frequency deviation, phase shift angle;

determining the presence of frequency compression, the number of channels, their mutual location in the signal spectrum and the frequency structure of each channel;

determining the presence and parameters of parasitic modulation.

In addition, the results of spectral analysis are used to extract a useful signal, that is, to determine and select filter and demodulator parameters.

Spectral analysis equipment. Spectral analysis equipment consists of a set of devices that allow you to find signals in a given band and determine their frequency parameters. The main device in spectral analysis is a spectral analyzer.

A spectral analyzer allows you to measure the frequency and amplitude of each of the sinusoidal oscillations that make up the complex signal being analyzed.

In addition to the analyzer, frequency counters, oscillographs, and other measuring instruments can be used in spectral analysis.

Analysis methods. Spectral analysis of signals can be performed in three different ways: parallel (simultaneous), sequential, and combined.

Parallel analysis is performed using identical narrow-band filters (high-quality resonators), each of which is tuned to a specific frequency. Since the measurement is performed simultaneously, the components of the spectrum are separated in each filter, depending on which spectrum it is tuned to.

Sequential analysis is an analysis performed sequentially over time, in which the frequency band under investigation is measured sequentially using tunable filters. The filter is tuned to different frequencies in a sequential manner, and with each new tuning, it separates the next spectral components.

In some cases, the two above-mentioned methods of analysis can be implemented together in one device. As a result, a third, combinational method of analysis is formed. According to the analysis method, spectrum analyzers are divided into parallel, serial and combinational analyzers.

To date, as a result of the development of microelectronics, circuit engineering and information technology, digital high-speed spectrum analyzers have been produced. These analyzers can not only determine the spectral composition of the signal, but also store the determined characteristics in memory, process it and perform many other operations in real time.

Even, using the capabilities of a personal computer and its standard sound card, it is possible to process signals with a frequency band of up to 20 kHz. This means that all types of signals transmitted over telephone lines (300 - 3400 GHz) can be fully technically analyzed using a computer and special programs installed on it.

The mathematical foundations of spectral analysis In many cases, the simplest electrical signal, which at first glance is considered very simple, can be a very difficult problem to express using mathematical formulas. Therefore, an original method is used in radio electronics and communications engineering. According to this method, any complex real signal is replaced by idealized mathematical models expressed using elementary functions. As a result, an instrument is created that allows you to analyze the passage of signals through radio circuits. And vice versa, the task of reconstructing complex signals from mathematical models based on these elementary functions also finds its solution. The founder of this idea is the French physicist and mathematician J.B. Fourier, who lived 200 years ago. Before explaining the idea proposed by Fourier, let's consider a system of elementary orthogonal functions, each of which is expressed on the basis of one similar

function (function-prototype). Similar functions play the role of "building blocks" of the signal being analyzed.

The most convenient way is to express the analytical representation of the signal being analyzed using a system of interconnected elementary functions. These elementary functions, in turn, are called basis functions: $v_i(t)$

$$v_0(t), v_1(t), v_2(t), v_3(t), \dots, v_i(t), \dots$$

Here, $i=1, 2, 3, \dots$

If the selected basis function system $v_i(t)$ has the property of orthonormalization (orthogonality and normalization), it becomes easier to represent the analyzed signal $u(t)$ with elementary functions. In mathematics, such a basis function system is called an orthonormalized basis. We will define the properties of orthogonality and normalization of functions.

The functions $u(t)$ and $v(t)$ are said to be orthogonal in the time intervals t_1 and t_2 if their scalar products are equal to zero. That is, the integral of their products:

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} u(t)v(t)dt = 0$$

when the condition is met that neither of the functions $u(t)$ nor $v(t)$ is equal to zero.

Any two functions $v_i(t)$ and $v_k(t)$ taken from an orthogonal system are said to be normalized if the following condition is met:

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} v_i(t)v_k(t)dt = \begin{cases} 1, & i = k; \\ 0, & i \neq k. \end{cases}$$

Thus, Fourier, having proved the theorem based on the idea he proposed, came to the following conclusion: any function varying in time can be expressed as a sum of finite or infinite harmonics with different amplitudes, frequencies and initial phases.

The fact that the voltage or current in an electrical circuit can be obtained as a function varying over time made it possible to apply this idea to signal analysis in radio electronics and communications. Describing a complex physical quantity (signal) as a sum of simple harmonics may seem implausible at first glance. As a simple proof, we will see the example presented in the figure below.

The figure below shows the oscillograms of three separate signals. The signals $u_2(t)$ and $u_3(t)$ are simple harmonic signals with frequencies that differ by a factor of two, while the signal $u_1(t)$ is a fairly complex signal. In fact, $u_1(t)=u_2(t)+u_3(t)$, that is, this complex signal is formed from the sum of two simple harmonic signals.

Let an arbitrary continuous signal $u(t)$ be changing in a given time interval t_1 and t_2 . Then, using the system of ideal orthonormalized functions in formula (5), this continuous signal $u(t)$ can be expressed using a generalized Fourier series:

$$u(t) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} c_i v_i(t),$$

where, c_i is a constant coefficient.

To determine the c_i constant coefficients of the series, we choose one of the bases corresponding to formula (5), for example, an arbitrary k -digit basis $v_k(t)$. We multiply both sides of the expression by the selected basis and integrate over the time interval under investigation:

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} u(t) v_k(t) dt = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} c_i \int_{t_1}^{t_2} v_i(t) v_k(t) dt$$

According to formula (5), in all cases where $i \neq k$ the right-hand side of expression (6) takes the value zero. Only when $i = k$ the right-hand side of the expression is non-zero, that is, equal to 1. Therefore,

$$c_k = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} u(t) v_k(t) dt \quad (6)$$

The coefficients c_k calculated for all k together give the spectral characteristic of the signal $u(t)$ being analyzed.

Fig. 1. a) complex signal; b) and c) simple harmonic signal

As an example, let us consider the spectral composition of a simple periodic signal, a sequence of pulses (Figure 24). As is known, a periodic signal is a signal that repeats itself after a certain fixed time. A periodic signal can be expressed as follows:

$$u(t) = u(t+nT), \quad (1-0)$$

where, T is the pulse repetition period, $n=0, 1, 2, \dots$.

In general, a sequence of periodically repeating pulses can be written in the following form:

$$u(t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} u_0(t-nT) \quad . \quad 1-1)$$

where, $u_0(t)$ - is the shape of a single pulse, which is characterized by such quantities as $h=E$ - amplitude, τ_i - duration, and $T=1/F$ - repetition period.

Figure 2. Periodic signal.

When representing periodic signals using their spectra, harmonic functions are used as the most convenient orthonormalized basis system:

$$\sqrt{\frac{1}{T}}, \sqrt{\frac{2}{T}} \cos \omega_1 t, \sqrt{\frac{2}{T}} \sin \omega_1 t, \dots, \sqrt{\frac{2}{T}} \cos n \omega_1 t, \sqrt{\frac{2}{T}} \sin n \omega_1 t, \quad (6)$$

where, $w_1 = \frac{2\pi}{T}$ - the repetition frequency of the pulses.

We represent a periodic signal using the most commonly used method, namely the trigonometric representation of the Fourier series:

$$u(t) = \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n \cos n \omega_1 t + b_n \sin n \omega_1 t) \quad (7)$$

In formula (7) there are the following components of the signal:

constant component:

In radio engineering, the spectral component with frequency w_1 is called the first (fundamental) harmonic of the signal, and the spectral components with frequency $nw_1 (n > 1)$ are called the higher harmonics of the signal.

If the signal under consideration is even, i.e. $u(t) = u(-t)$, then the Fourier series does not contain the b_n coefficients of the sinusoidal components (because they are zero), and conversely, if the signal is odd, the series does not contain the a_n coefficients of the cosinusoidal components.

To facilitate its mathematical expression, formula (7) is often expressed in the following form:

$$u(t) = A_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n \cos(n \omega_1 t - \varphi_n) \quad (11)$$

where, $A_0 = a_0/2$, $A_n = \sqrt{a_n^2 + b_n^2}$ - amplitude and $\varphi_n = \arctg(b_n/a_n)$ - The initial phase of the nth harmonic of the signal.

In addition to the trigonometric form of the Fourier series discussed above, the complex form of the Fourier series is also widely used in radio electronics and signal theory:

$$u(t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} C_n e^{jn\omega t}, \quad (12)$$

where

$$C_n = \dot{C}_n = C_n(j\omega) = \frac{1}{T} \int_{-T/2}^{T/2} u(t) e^{-jn\omega t} dt \quad (13)$$

n is the complex amplitude of the harmonic.

If we pay attention to formula (12), the spectral composition of the signal contains frequencies with positive and negative signs, but in nature there is no frequency with a negative sign. Therefore, the negative frequency is not a physical concept, but a mathematical abstraction. The negative frequency arises as a result of representing the signal using the complex Fourier series. If we pass from the

complex representation to the trigonometric representation, the negative frequency loses its essence.

Figure 3. Periodic signal spectra: a) amplitude; b) phase; c) complex.

It is much more convenient to analyze the spectral composition of signals using its graphical representation (Fig. 61). In signal theory, amplitude-frequency and phase-frequency spectra are widely used. The spectrum that provides sufficient information about the signal is the amplitude-frequency spectrum. Because with the help of this spectrum, it is possible to determine the quantitative

value of the constituent harmonics in the analyzed signal. The $1/T$ product in front of the integral is not used;

Figure 4. Doubling the period of the pulse sequence causes the signal spectrum to become denser.

Fast Fourier transform. To calculate one coefficient of a discrete Fourier transform, it is necessary to perform N complex multiplications and additions. Therefore, calculating an FDO of N coefficients requires performing N^2 “multiplication-addition” operations. The number of operations increases proportionally to the square of the FDO size. If N is not a prime number and it is possible to divide it into factors, the calculation process can be accelerated. To do this, the set of numbers being analyzed is divided into separate parts, and the FDO coefficients of each part are calculated, and the results are combined. Calculating FDO coefficients in this way is called the fast Fourier transform (FFT) and is the most widely used method in practice.

In turn, the fast Fourier transform (FTO'), depending on the type of division of the signal sequence into parts, is divided into time-truncated FTO' and frequency-truncated FTO'.

Time-truncated FTO'

Let's say N is an even number, we express formula (8) in the form of two, that is, the sum of even and odd numbers belonging to the elements of the initial sequence:

$$\dot{X}(n) = \sum_{m=0}^{\frac{N}{2}-1} x(2m)e^{-j\frac{2\pi 2mn}{N}} + \sum_{m=0}^{\frac{N}{2}-1} x(2m+1)e^{-j\frac{2\pi(2m+1)n}{N}}$$

To make the formula look more convenient $y(m)=x(2m)$ and $z(m)=x(2m+1)$ introduce definitions such as, and also from the second sum $e^{-j\frac{2\pi m}{N}}$ extract the common factor:

$$\dot{X}(n) = \sum_{m=0}^{\frac{N}{2}-1} y(m)e^{-j\frac{2\pi mn}{N/2}} + e^{-j\frac{2\pi n}{N}} \sum_{m=0}^{\frac{N}{2}-1} z(m)e^{-j\frac{2\pi mn}{N/2}} \quad (9)$$

In conclusion, this article analyzes the spectral analysis of a signal, its theoretical foundations, practical applications and technical devices. Spectral analysis plays an important role in determining the frequency composition of signals and studying the characteristics necessary for the transmission systems of the analyzed signal. Analysis using spectral analysis technologies, including the Fourier series, allows you to determine the analytical form of the signal, which provides information necessary for the effective control of complex systems and their optimization. In addition, spectral analyzers, frequency counters, oscilloscopes and other measuring instruments are widely used to determine the spectral composition of a signal and measure its parameters. With the development of digital technologies and microelectronics, digital high-speed spectral analyzers allow for real-time signal analysis, which further increases the efficiency of telecommunication systems. The Fourier series and its various forms, including the fast Fourier transform (FFT), are an important tool for analyzing signals and determining their spectral composition. These methods allow signals to be divided into parts and their amplitude and frequency parameters to be determined, which ensures the accuracy and efficiency of complex signal analysis. At the same time, spectral analysis, in addition to analyzing signals, is also used to improve the design and efficiency of telecommunication systems. The development of digital technologies and the possibilities of computer-aided signal analysis are of great importance for the future of modern information technologies. As a result, spectral analysis provides all the parameters necessary for a complete and accurate understanding of signals and allows them to be effectively used in various fields, including telecommunications, information technologies and digital systems. As a result of the integration of information and communication technologies, a new

knowledge environment is being created. There comes a time when mastering the techniques of intellectual labor that generate creativity becomes an important factor. The value of modern information and multimedia technologies lies in their versatility and versatility. However, these technologies, with all their capabilities, only provide tools that make the teacher's work more effective. How to unlock this potential for the educational process is the main multifaceted problem of improving education on the basis of information technologies. Education based on computer technologies is based primarily on the technical infrastructure - a computer (as a means of storing and presenting educational information). Therefore, one of the principles that should be taken into account when creating electronic applications is the principle of distribution of educational material. Computer training programs have long been used in education as additional educational tools. However, in distance learning, the computer becomes the main didactic tool, and instead of various educational programs, an integrated interactive course is needed that represents all educational information, has a sufficient level of completeness. The principle of interactivity of educational material is the second important principle that should be taken into account when developing educational and methodological support for distance education. Modern educational technologies based on the widespread use of computing technologies have enormous potential. However, the full use of computerized technologies requires a serious study of the problem of interaction between humans and technical means.

REFERENCES:

1. Bespalko, V.P. Education and training with the participation of computers / V.P. Bespalko. - Moscow: Ed. Moscow Psychological and Social Institute, 2002. - 352 pages.
2. Zakharova, I.G. Information technologies in education: a textbook for students of higher educational institutions / I.G. Zakharov. - 3rd ed., - Moscow: "Academy", 2007. - 192 p.
3. Zimina, O.V. Printed and electronic manuals in modern higher education: theory, methodology, practice. / O.V. Zimina, A.I. Kirillov. - Moscow: MPEI, 2003. - 167 p.
4. Krasilnikov I.V. Information aspects of the development and use of electronic educational tools at the university. Monograph / I.V. Krasilnikov. - Moscow: "RCTU", 2007. - 114 p.

5. Azlarov A.S. Mathematical analysis: a manual for the direction of applied mathematics and computer science 2001.-423 p.
6. Collection of lectures delivered by the Center for Radioelectronic Systems and Information. 2003.